

CAUSATION, 16(12): 5–53
DOI:[10.5281/zenodo.5779506](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779506)
Received: December 12, 2021,
Accepted: December 14, 2021
Published: December 14, 2021
ISSN: 1863-9542

COVID-19 vaccines - a great leap forward?

Research article

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Abstract:

Background:

The tension between science and ideology seems as old as science itself. To what extent is science used/misused to support certain ideologies? Does ideologies or purely material interests have any influence on the results of scientific research, and to what extent?

Methods:

Logically inconsistent scientific methods can contribute more to the formation of ideologies than to reliable scientific knowledge. In the long run, such methods open the doors wide for ideologies to be part of the formation of science and that science itself evolves backward into pure ideology.

Results:

The statistical method of calculating the vaccine efficacy has been re-evaluated.

Conclusion:

Mathematically, today's method of calculating the vaccine efficacy is logically not consistent.

Keywords: Vaccine efficacy; Study design; Bias; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k

1. Introduction

An efficacious drug, vaccine et cetera is of vital importance in order to prevent morbidity and mortality of people. However, this issue raises the question under which conditions and to what extent might we treat drugs, vaccines et cetera as effective ^{1, 2, 3, 4} at all? How well does the candidate drug or vaccine et cetera prevent against a certain event for which it was developed? Are there any proven methods we might rely on thoroughly which undoubtedly allow us to judge whether or not the candidate drug or vaccine et cetera is safe, effective and so on? We must bear in mind that the mathematical deduction of (vaccine) efficacy is more than 100 years old, having been proposed by Greenwood and Yule (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) in 1915. The thinking behind Greenwood and Yule is quite clear. For no reason whatsoever, vaccine efficacy is best measured by a double-blind, randomized, clinical controlled trials where the exposure to infection in the unvaccinated and the vaccinated must be equal⁵. Why should this be so? In general, a double-blind, placebo-controlled trial performed on human subjects to generate data on the safety and efficacy of various drugs et cetera is regarded as the gold standard in medical research. However, such a trial has its weaknesses⁶ too. At this stage, there is no clear logical or mathematical evidence for such a need. Nonetheless, taking into account the most recent research (see Barukčić, 2021a,b,c), it is questionable whether the scientific attitude of Greenwood and Yule (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) is objectively either justified or desirable. Therefore, more research is needed to re-investigate this matter.

Since its outbreak, the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus type 2 (SARS-CoV-2) which originated from Wuhan in China, with its alarming-spreading speed resulted meanwhile in a sharp rise⁷ in the accumulative number of infections and deaths worldwide. Regrettably, COVID-19 has already killed more than 4 million people, while more than 200 million people were infected. The urgent need for safe and effective COVID-19 vaccines to achieve rapid herd immunity is more than evident. On the long run, it is appropriate to prevent SARS-CoV-2 from escaping from human immune surveillance. In general, mRNA vaccines, DNA vaccines, viral vector vaccines, inactivated virus vaccines are used with a very controversial effectiveness and safety. CNBC reported that the protection of BNT162b2 mRNA vaccine against a SARS-CoV-2 infection in Israel is about 39%⁸. Regardless of whether or not these contradictions might be rooted in deeply questionable and dubious mathematical-statistical methods⁹, the same should not prevent us from taking a great leap forward in a timely manner in order not to lose too many people to this natural disaster. So, at this point, I will attempt to offer a satisfactory answer to some deeply questionable and dubious mathematical-statistical methods.

¹PMID: 33691913

²PMID: 33125914

³PMID: 33923054

⁴PMID: 34269175

⁵PMID: 1899778

⁶PMID: 9158270

⁷PMID: 34776011

⁸Berkeley Lovelace Jr., CNBC, Published Fri, Jul 23 2021:23 PM

⁹PMID: 20402594

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. Covid-19 vaccines

Wearing an appropriate filtering face piece (FFP) or FFP2 mask¹⁰ or better FFP3 mask in the community is one of the measures which might provide an excellent protection for others and oneself against a SARS-CoV-2 infection. However, SARS-CoV-2 vaccines are effective in reducing severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) too. View patient demanded by themselves to be tested for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. Table 1 represents slightly changed, fictional values of view patients, which are based on values that have actually been collected. ECLIA (Elecsys^(R) Roche) test has been used to detect SARS-CoV-2 antibodies (including IgG) against the receptor binding domain (RBD) of the spike (S) protein of SARS-CoV-2. As reported by Roche, the unit U / mL of the Elecsys Anti-SARS-CoV-2 S assay correlates very well with the ‘binding antibody units’(BAU) of the WHO’s first international standard for anti-SARS-CoV-2 immunoglobulin. The Roche conversion factor is: $x \text{ (U/ml)} = 0.972 * y \text{ (BAU/ml)}$ or $y \text{ (BAU/ml)} = x \text{ (U/ml)} / 0.972$. The following overview (table 1) shows a rather pronounced variation in the effectiveness of the production of the antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 as induces by Covid-19 vaccines.

Table 1. Fictive, SARS-CoV-2 antibodies (including IgG) derived from real world data

BAU/ml							
10000							
5000						5422	
4000							
3000							
2000					2595		
1000			1486	1549			
900							
800							
700							
600							
500							
400							
300							
200	210		226				
100							
0							
	Covid-19 infection control (Patient 1)	Third dose: Second dose: First dose :	AstraZeneca (Patient 2)	BionTech (Patient 3)	BionTech (Patient 4)	BionTech (Patient 5)	BionTech (Patient 6)

¹⁰PMID: 34857639

2.1.2. ChAdOx1 nCov-19 Covid-19 vaccine

“There were seven deaths considered unrelated to vaccination (two in the ChAdOx1 nCov-19 group and five in the control group) ... ”¹¹ with “... 12282 participants in the ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 group and ... 11962 participants in the control group”¹².

Table 2. ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine and Covid-19 death.

		Covid-19 death		
		YES	NO	
ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine	YES	2	12280	12282
	NO	5	11957	11962
		7	24237	24244

Statistical analysis.

Causal relationship k =	-0,0075083447
p Value left tailed (HGD) =	0,2158443
p (EXCL) =	0,9999175054
p (EXCL) approx.=	0,9998371601
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A _t) =	0,0003
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B _t) =	0,5714
p Value (EXCL) =	0,000082

Relative risk (RR).

RR (nc) =	0,3896
RR (sc) =	0,5639
Vaccine efficacy (%) =	61,0422

Additional measures.

OR =	0,9998
IOR =	-0,4360

Study design.

p(IOU)=	0,493111698
p(IOI)=	0,50631084

ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine efficacy calculated due to Greenwood and Yule (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) is

$$\begin{aligned}
 VE(\text{ChAdOx1nCoV} - 19 \text{ vaccine, Covid} - 19 \text{ death}) &\equiv \left(1 - \left(\frac{a_t \times A_t}{A_t \times c_t} \right) \right) \times 100 \\
 &\equiv \left(1 - \left(\frac{2 \times 11962}{12282 \times 5} \right) \right) \times 100 \quad (1) \\
 &\equiv 61,04217554 \%
 \end{aligned}$$

¹¹PMID: 33617777

¹²PMID: 33617777

The placebo group independent approximate (see [Barukčić, 2021a](#)) drug i.e. vaccine efficacy (VE approx.) of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine follows approximately (see equation 58) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 VE \text{ approx. } (A_t, B_t) &\geq \left(1 - \frac{N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(A_t)}\right) \times 100 \\
 &\geq \left(1 - \left(\frac{2}{12282}\right)\right) \times 100 \\
 &\geq 99,98371601\%
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

In other words, less than $(1 - 0,9998371601) \times 2026198 = 330$ of 2026198 ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccinated inhabitants of Scotland should die due to Cvoid-19. In reality, 188 of 2026198 inhabitants of Scotland died due to Cvoid-19 even if vaccinated by ChAdOx1 nCoV-19. Model's precision is very accurate. The deviation of the predicted maximum value (330) from the true, known and measured value (188) is minimal. We obtain, $100 \times \left(\frac{330 - 188}{2026198}\right) = 0,0070081996\%$ which is as such very close to the observed value. The original vaccine efficacy of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 published has been about 61 %. The difference is factually unfounded, extremely dangerous and beyond any relation to reality. It is therefore more than necessary to consider urgently to reduce drastically any further use of the vaccine efficacy method as advocated by Greenwood and Yule ([Greenwood and Yule, 1915](#)). The index of independence ([Barukčić, 2019a](#)) is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 IOI(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{A_t + B_t}{N}\right) - 1\right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{12282 + 24237}{24244}\right) - 1\right) \\
 &\equiv 0,50631084
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

2.1.3. ChAdOx1 nCov-19 Covid-19 vaccine ex post?

Vaccines are effective in preventing COVID-19 deaths. Grange et al. (see [Grange et al., 2021](#)) investigated COVID-19-related deaths in 3 273 336 individuals in Scotland who were fully vaccinated by Aug 18, 2021. Scotland's 2011 census population has been 5 313 600. Grange et al. are writing: "Of the 3 273 336 individuals in Scotland who were fully vaccinated by Aug 18, 2021 (73.6% of the eligible population), 1 205 642 individuals received two doses of BNT162b2 and 2 026 198 individuals received two doses of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19. As there were no deaths among the 41 496 individuals who received two doses of mRNA-1273 (Moderna) vaccine during the study period, they were not further considered in this analysis. 236 deaths in fully vaccinated people were recorded (0.007% of the total vaccinated): 47 (0.004%) of those individuals had received BNT162b2 (median age 74.0 years [IQR 69.0–89.0]), and 188 (0.009%) individuals had received ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 (80.0 years [73.0–86.0])." (see [Grange et al., 2021](#)).

Table 3. ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine and Covid-19 death (Study Grange et al., 2021).

		Covid-19 death		
		YES	NO	
ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine	YES	188	2026010	2026198
	NO	64812	3239590	3304402
		65000	5265600	5330600

Statistical analysis.

Causal relationship k =	-0,0863395897
p Value left tailed (HGD) =	0,0000000
p (EXCL) =	0,9999647319
p (EXCL) approx. =	0,9990729692
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A _t) =	0,0174
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B _t) =	0,5438
p Value (EXCL) =	0,0000352681

Relative risk (RR).

RR (nc) =	0,0047
RR (sc) =	0,0075
Vaccine efficacy (%) =	99,5269

Additional measures.

OR =	0,9999
IOR =	-0,9924

Study design.

p(IOU)=	0,607699321
p(IOI)=	0,367913181

The hyper-geometric distribution describes the probability of x successes in N **draws without replacement** while the same distribution is valid for all sample sizes. In contrast to the hyper-geometric

distribution, the binomial distribution which describes the probability of x successes in N **draws with replacement** . The left tailed p Value is used when the alternative to independence is that there is a **negative relationship** between the variables investigated. The left tailed p Value (no replacement, hyper-geometric distribution) is calculated as follows:

$$pValue_{\text{left tailed}}(X \leq 188) \equiv \sum_{t=0}^{188} \left(\frac{\binom{2026198}{t} \times \binom{5330600-2026198}{65000-t}}{\binom{5330600}{65000}} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\equiv 0,0000000000$$

In other words, both events, ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine and Covid-19 death , might occur together at the same (period of) time t purely by chance at a probability rate of 0,0000000000. The index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) is calculated as

$$IOI(A_t, B_t) \equiv \left(\left(\frac{A_t + B_t}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\equiv \left(\left(\frac{2026198 + 5265600}{5330600} \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$\equiv 0,367913181$$

The placebo group independent approximate(see Barukčić, 2021a) drug i.e. vaccine efficacy (VE approx.) of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine follows approximately (see equation 58) as

$$VE_{\text{approx.}}(A_t, B_t) \geq \left(1 - \frac{N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(A_t)} \right) \times 100 \quad (6)$$

$$\geq \left(1 - \left(\frac{188}{2026198} \right) \right) \times 100$$

$$\geq 99,90729692\%$$

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Bernoulli distribution

Let a **random variable**(Gosset, 1914) X denote something like a function defined on a probability space, which itself maps from the sample space(Neyman and Pearson, 1933) to the real numbers. A single event distribution is more or less a discrete probability distribution of any random variable X which takes a certain (observer independent) single value X_t at a **Bernoulli trial**(Uspensky, 1937, p. 45) (period of time) t with the probability $p(X_t)$. The same random variable X takes a certain single anti value \underline{X}_t at a Bernoulli trial (period of time) t with the probability $1-p(X_t)$. There are conditions in nature where a random variable X can take only the values either $+0$ or $+1$. Under these conditions the random variable X takes the value 1 with probability $p(X_t = +1)$ and the value 0 with probability $q(X_t = +0) = 1 - p(X_t = +1)$ while the single event distribution passes over into the **Bernoulli distribution**, named after Swiss mathematician Jacob Bernoulli(Bernoulli, 1713). Less formally, many times, the Bernoulli distribution is represented by a (possibly not biased) coin toss where 1 and 0 would represent ‘heads’ and ‘tails’(or vice versa), respectively. However, the relationship between random variables (Gosset, 1914) can be investigated by many (Gosset, 1908) methods, including the tools of probability theory, too.

Definition 2.1 (Two by two table of single event random variables).

The two by two or contingency table which has been introduced by Karl Pearson(Pearson, 1904) in 1904 harbours still a large variety of topics and debates. Central to this is the problem to apply the laws of classical logic on data sets, which concerns the justification of inferences which extrapolate from sample data to general facts. Nevertheless, a contingency table is still an appropriate theoretical model too for studying the relationships between random variables, including *Bernoulli*(Bernoulli, 1713) (*i.e.* $+0/+1$) *distributed random variables* existing or occurring at the same *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t .

In this context, let a random variable A at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t , denoted by A_t , indicate a risk factor, a condition, a cause et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(A_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t . Let $E(A_t)$ denote the expectation value of A_t . In general it is

$$p(A_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \quad (7)$$

The expectation value $E(A_t)$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv A_t \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t)) \\ &\equiv (A_t \times p(a_t)) + (A_t \times p(b_t)) \\ &\equiv E(a_t) + E(b_t) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{A}_t) \equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \tag{10}$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{A}_t)$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv A_t \times (p(c_t) + p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times p(c_t)) + (A_t \times p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(c_t) + E(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Let a random variable B at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t , denoted by B_t , indicate an outcome, a conditioned, an effect et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(B_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t . Let $E(B_t)$ denote the expectation value of B_t . In general it is

$$p(B_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) \tag{13}$$

The expectation value $E(B_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv B_t \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv (B_t \times p(a_t)) + (B_t \times p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(a_t) + E(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{B}_t) \equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \tag{16}$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{B}_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv B_t \times (p(b_t) + p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv (B_t \times p(b_t)) + (B_t \times p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(b_t) + E(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Let $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Let $p(b_t) = p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Let $p(c_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\ &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\ &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(c_t) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\ &\equiv (\neg A_t \times B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\ &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\ &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\ &\equiv p(c_t) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Let $p(d_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \\ &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\ &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(d_t) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\ &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\ &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\ &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\ &\equiv p(d_t) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

In general, it is

$$p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv +1 \quad (27)$$

Table 4 provide us with an overview of the definitions above.

Table 4. The two by two table of Bernoulli random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

2.2.2. Binomial random variables

The binomial distribution is a discrete probability distribution with more than one single Bernoulli trial (e.g. more than one single coin toss) and as such a special case of the Bernoulli distribution. As it turns out, a Bernoulli trial (see [Uspensky, 1937](#)) is an experiment which can have only one of two possible outcomes, either the one or its own other. In general, a Bernoulli trial, usually phrased in terms of true and not true (i.e. false), is known to be one of the simplest experiments which can be conducted. Under conditions where x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are independent Bernoulli(p) distributed random variables, the random variable X defined by $X_1 = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n$ has a Binomial(n, p) distribution. The geometric random variable X_2 describes the total number of failures before observing the first success. **Example.** Toss a coin repeatedly until observing the first success.

Definition 2.2 (Two by two table of Binomial random variables).

Let $a = E(a)$, $b = E(b)$, $c = E(c)$, $d = E(d)$, $A = E(A)$, $\underline{A} = E(\underline{A})$, $B = E(B)$, and $\underline{B} = E(\underline{B})$ denote expectation values. Under conditions where *the probability of an event, an outcome, a success et cetera is constant from Bernoulli trial to Bernoulli trial t* , it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 A = E(A) &= N \times E(A_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (A_t \times p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv a + b \\
 &\equiv E(a) + E(b)
 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{A} = E(\underline{A}) &= N \times E(\underline{A}_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv a + d \\
 &\equiv E(a) + E(d)
 \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 B = E(B) &= N \times E(B_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (B_t \times p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv a + c \\
 &\equiv E(a) + E(c)
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

where N might denote the population or even the sample size.

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{B} &= E(\underline{B}) = N \times E(\underline{B}_t) \\ &\equiv N \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv b + d \\ &\equiv E(b) + E(d)\end{aligned}\tag{31}$$

Furthermore, it is

$$a = E(a) \equiv N \times (E(A_t)) \equiv N \times (p(A_t))\tag{32}$$

and

$$b = E(b) \equiv N \times (E(B_t)) \equiv N \times (p(B_t))\tag{33}$$

and

$$c = E(c) \equiv N \times (E(c_t)) \equiv N \times (p(c_t))\tag{34}$$

and

$$d = E(d) \equiv N \times (E(d_t)) \equiv N \times (p(d_t))\tag{35}$$

and

$$a + b + c + d \equiv A + \underline{A} \equiv B + \underline{B} \equiv N\tag{36}$$

An overview of Binomial random variables is provided to us by the contingency table (see table 5). In 1904, Karl Pearson (1857-1936), an English mathematician and biostatistician, introduced the two by two or contingency table (see [Pearson, 1904](#)) The contingency table offers a methodological possibility to illustrate the laws of classical logic with respect to data sets.

Table 5. The two by two table of Binomial random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
A_t	TRUE	a	b	A
	FALSE	c	d	<u>A</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

2.2.3. Independence

Definition 2.3 (Independence).

In general, an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t need not but can be independent of the existence or of the occurrence of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t . Mathematically, independence ([Kolmogoroff, 1933](#), [Moivre, 1718](#)) in terms of probability theory is defined at the same (period of)

time t (i.e. Bernoulli trial t) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \wedge B_t) &\equiv p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \wedge B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t))}{N} \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

2.2.4. Dependence

Definition 2.4 (Dependence).

The dependence of events (Barukčić, 1989, p. 57-61) is defined as

$$p\left(\underbrace{A_t \wedge B_t \wedge C_t \wedge \dots}_n\right) \equiv \sqrt[n]{\underbrace{p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \times p(C_t) \times \dots}_n} \quad (38)$$

2.3. Biostatistics and Epidemiology

2.3.1. Relative risk (RR)

Relative risk (RR_{nc})

Definition 2.5 (Relative risk (RR_{nc})).

The degree of association between the two binomial variables can be assessed by a number of very different coefficients, the relative (Cornfield, 1951, Sadowsky et al., 1953) risk is one (Barukčić, 2021e) of them. In general, relative risk RR_{nc}, which provides some evidence of a necessary condition, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} &\equiv \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)}}{\frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)}} \\ &\equiv \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(c_t) \times p(A_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotA_t)}{N \times p(c_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{a_t \times (NotA_t)}{c_t \times A_t} \\ &\equiv \frac{EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

That what scientist generally understand by relative risk is the ratio of a probability of an event occurring with an exposure versus the probability of an event occurring without an exposure. In other words,

relative risk = (probability(event in exposed group)) / (probability(the same event in not exposed group)).

A $RR(A_t, B_t) = +1$ means that exposure does not affect the outcome or both are independent of each other while $RR(A_t, B_t)$ less than +1 means that the risk of the outcome is decreased by the exposure. In this context, an $RR(A_t, B_t)$ greater than +1 denotes that the risk of the outcome is increased by the exposure. Widely known problems with odds ratio and relative risk are already documented in literature.

Relative risk (RR (sc))

Definition 2.6 (Relative risk (RR (sc))).

The relative risk (sc), which provides some evidence of a sufficient condition, is calculated from the point of view of an outcome and is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} &\equiv \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)}}{\frac{p(b_t)}{p(NotB_t)}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotB_t)}{p(b_t) \times p(B_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotB_t)}{N \times p(b_t) \times N \times p(B_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a_t \times (NotB_t)}{b_t \times B_t} \\
 &\equiv \frac{OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

Relative risk reduction (RRR)

Definition 2.7 (Relative risk reduction (RRR)).

$$\begin{aligned} RRR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \\ &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Vaccine efficacy (VE)

Definition 2.8 (Vaccine efficacy (VE)).

Vaccine efficacy is defined as the percentage reduction of a disease in a vaccinated group of people as compared to an unvaccinated group of people.

$$\begin{aligned} VE(A_t, B_t) &\equiv 100 \times (1 - RR(A_t, B_t)) \\ &\equiv 100 \times \left(\frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

Historically, vaccine efficacy has been designed to evaluate the efficacy of a certain vaccine by Greenwood and Yule in 1915 for the cholera and typhoid vaccines (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) and best measured using double-blind, randomized, clinical controlled trials. However, the calculated vaccine efficacy is depending too much on the study design, can lead to erroneous conclusions and is only of very limited value.

Experimental event rate (EER)

Definition 2.9 (Experimental event rate (EER)).

$$EER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \quad (43)$$

Definition 2.10 (Control event rate (CER)).

$$CER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} = \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} \quad (44)$$

Absolute risk reduction (ARR)

Definition 2.11 (Absolute risk reduction (ARR)).

$$\begin{aligned}
 ARR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} \\
 &= \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} - \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \\
 &= CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

Absolute risk increase (ARI)

Definition 2.12 (Absolute risk increase (ARI)).

$$\begin{aligned}
 ARI(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} \\
 &= EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{46}$$

Number needed to treat (NNT)

Definition 2.13 (Number needed to treat (NNT)).

$$NNT(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)} \tag{47}$$

An ideal number needed to treat (Cook and Sackett, 1995, Laupacis et al., 1988), mathematically the reciprocal of the absolute risk reduction, is $NNT = 1$. Under these circumstances, everyone improves with a treatment, while no one improves with control. A higher number needed to treat indicates more or less a treatment which is less effective.

Number needed to harm (NNH)

Definition 2.14 (Number needed to harm (NNH)).

$$NNH(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t)} \tag{48}$$

The number needed to harm (Massel and Cruickshank, 2002), mathematically the inverse of the absolute risk increase, indicates at the end how many patients need to be exposed to a certain factor, in order to observe a harm in one patient that would not otherwise have been harmed.

Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)

Definition 2.15 (Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)).

$$OPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + c_t} \quad (49)$$

Control prevalence rate (CPR)

Definition 2.16 (Control prevalence rate (CPR)).

$$CPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(b_t)}{p(B_t)} = \frac{b_t}{b_t + d_t} \quad (50)$$

Bias and confounding is present to some degree in all research. In order to assess the relationship of exposure with a disease or an outcome, a fictive control group (i.e. of newborn or of young children et cetera) can be of use too. Under certain circumstances, even a $CPR = 0$ is imaginable.

Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)

Definition 2.17 (Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)).

$$APR(A_t, B_t) \equiv CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (51)$$

Absolute prevalence increase (API)

Definition 2.18 (Absolute prevalence increase (API)).

$$API(A_t, B_t) \equiv OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (52)$$

Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)

Definition 2.19 (Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)).

$$\begin{aligned} RPR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)} \\ &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

The index NNS

Definition 2.20 (The index NNS).

$$NNS(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (54)$$

Mathematically, the index NNS is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence reduction.

The index NNI

Definition 2.21 (The index NNI).

$$NNI(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (55)$$

Mathematically, the index NNI is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence increase.

2.3.2. Odds ratio (OR)

Definition 2.22 (Odds ratio (OR)).

Odds ratios as an appropriate measure for estimating the relative risk have become widely used in medical reports of case-control studies. The odds ratio (Fisher, 1935, p. 50) is defined (Cox, 1958) as the ratio of the odds of an event occurring in one group with respect to the odds of its occurring in another group. Odds (Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 273) ratio (OR) is a measure of association which quantifies the relationship between two binomial distributed random variables (exposure vs. outcome) and is related to Yule's (Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 272) Q (Yule, 1912, p. 585/586). Two events A_t and B_t are regarded as independent if $(A_t, B_t) = 1$. Let

a_t = number of persons exposed to A_t and with disease B_t

b_t = number of persons exposed to A_t but without disease B_t

c_t = number of persons unexposed \underline{A}_t but with disease B_t

d_t = number of persons unexposed \underline{A}_t : and without disease B_t

$a_t + c_t$ = total number of persons with disease B_t (case-patients)

$b_t + d_t$ = total number of persons without disease B_t (controls).

Table 6. The two by two table of random variables

		Conditioned/Outcome B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition/Exposure A_t	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	c_t	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	N_t

Hereafter, consider the table 6. The odds' ratio (OR) is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 OR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t}{b_t} \right) / \left(\frac{c_t}{d_t} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{56}$$

Remark 2.1. Odds ratios can support logical fallacies and cause difficulties in drawing logically consistent conclusions. The chorus of voices is growing, which demand the immediate ending (Knol, 2012, Sackett et al., 1996) of any use of Odds ratio.

Under conditions where ($b = 0$), the measure of association odds ratio will collapse, because we need to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 56. However, according to today's rules of mathematics, a division by zero is neither allowed nor generally accepted as possible. It does no harm to remind ourselves that in the case $b = 0$ the event A_t is a sufficient condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of objective reality. In fact, it would be a failure not to recognize how dangerous and less valuable odds ratio is.

Under conditions where ($c = 0$) odds ratio collapses too, because we need again to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 56. However, and again, today's rules of mathematics don't allow us a division by zero. In point of fact, in the case $c = 0$ it is more than necessary to point out that A_t is a necessary condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio or the cross-product ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of nature like necessary conditions. We can and need to overcome all the epistemological obstacles as backed by odds ratio entirety. Sooner rather than later, we should give up this measure of relationship completely.

2.4. Conditions

2.4.1. Exclusion relationship

Definition 2.23 (Exclusion relationship [EXCL]).

Mathematically, the exclusion (EXCL) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t | B_t)$ in terms of statistics and

probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{b + c + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + \underline{A}}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c + \underline{B}}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

Based on the 1913 Henry Maurice Sheffer (1882-1964) relationship, the Sheffer stroke (Nicod, 1917, Sheffer, 1913) usually denoted by \uparrow , it is $p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t)$ (see table 7). In general, a rough

Table 7. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (COVID-19) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Vaccine) A_t	TRUE	+0	$p(b_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

and only approximate estimate (see Barukčić, 2021a) of the mutually exclusive relationship is given by the equation

$$p(A_t | B_t) \geq +1 - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} \tag{58}$$

and under different conditions by the equation

$$p(A_t | B_t) \geq +1 - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)} \tag{59}$$

2.4.2. The goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.24 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about an exclusion relationship $p(A_t | B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c + d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\
&\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + 0 \\
&\equiv \frac{a^2}{A}
\end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

or just as

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\
&\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + 0 \\
&\equiv \frac{a^2}{B}
\end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of an exclusion relationship/distribution $p(A_t | B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis has to be accepted. Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction was not used under these circumstances.

2.4.3. The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.25 (The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship).

It is known that as a sample size, N , increases, a sampling distribution of a special test statistic approaches the normal distribution (central limit theorem). Under these circumstances, the left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of an exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
pValue_{lt}(A_t | B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t|B_t))} \\
&\equiv 1 - e^{-(a/N)}
\end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

A low p-value may provide some evidence of statistical significance.

2.4.4. Neither nor conditions

Definition 2.26 (Neither A_t nor B_t conditions [NOR]).

Mathematically, a neither A_t nor B_t condition (or rejection according to the French philosopher and logician Jean George Pierre Nicod (1893-1924), i.e. Jean Nicod's statement (Nicod, 1924)) relationship (NOR), denoted by $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N - \sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \wedge B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

2.4.5. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a neither nor condition relationship

Definition 2.27 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

A neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution). The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 may be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{A} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{A} + 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b + d))^2}{B} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + c) - B)^2}{B} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} + 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{65}$$

Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.4.6. The left-tailed p Value of a neither nor B condition relationship

Definition 2.28 (The left-tailed p Value of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 pValue_{lt}(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \downarrow B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-p(A_t \vee B_t)} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+b+c)/N)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{66}$$

where \vee may denote disjunction or logical inclusive or. In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. In general, it is $p(A_t \vee B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see table 8).

Table 8. Neither A_t nor B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	0	0
	NO	0	1	1
		0	1	1

2.4.7. Necessary condition

Definition 2.29 (Necessary condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]).

Mathematically, the necessary condition (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 15-28) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \times p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{A + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + \underline{B}}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{67}$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ indicates the expectation value of the necessary condition. In general, it is $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see Table 9).

Table 9. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	+0	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.2. A necessary condition A_t is characterized itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a,b, 2020a,b,c,d, Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020). **Example.** A human being cannot live without water. A human being cannot live without gaseous oxygen et cetera. Water itself is a necessary condition of human life. However, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of human life too. Thus far, even if water is given and even if water is a necessary condition of human life, without gaseous oxygen there will be no human life. In general, if a conditioned or an outcome B_t depends on the necessary condition A_t and equally on numerous other necessary conditions, an event B_t will not occur if A_t itself is not given independently of the occurrence of other necessary conditions.

2.4.8. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship

Definition 2.30 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, hypothesis about the conditio sine qua non relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution), first described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (Helmert, 1876) and later rediscovered by Karl Pearson (Pearson, 1900) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio sine qua non relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b+d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B}
 \end{aligned} \tag{68}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A}) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{69}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . It has not yet been finally clarified whether the use of Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.4.9. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship

Definition 2.31 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of the conditio sine qua non relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{70}$$

2.4.10. Sufficient condition

Definition 2.32 (Sufficient condition [*Conditio per quam*]).

Mathematically, the sufficient condition (IMP) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ in terms of

statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \times p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + c + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{B + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \rightarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + \underline{A}}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{71}$$

It is $p(A_t \succ B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 10).

Table 10. Sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	+0	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.3. A sufficient condition A_t is characterized by the property that another event B_t will occur if A_t is given, if A_t itself occurred (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a,b, 2020a,b,c,d, Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020). **Example.** The ground, the streets, the trees, human beings and many other objects too will become wet during heavy rain. Especially, **if** it is raining (event A_t), **then** human beings will become wet (event B_t). However, even if this is a common human wisdom, a human being equipped with an appropriate umbrella (denoted by R_t) need not become wet even during heavy rain. An appropriate umbrella (R_t) is similar to an event with the potential to counteract the occurrence of another event (B_t) and can be understood something as an **anti-dot** of another event. In other words, an appropriate umbrella is an antidote of the effect of rain on human body, an appropriate umbrella has the potential to protect humans from the effect of rain on their body. It is a good rule of thumb that the following relationship

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) + p(R_t \wedge B_t) \equiv +1 \tag{72}$$

indicates that R_t is an antidote of A_t . However, taking a shower, swimming in a lake et cetera may make human hair wet too. More than anything else, however, these events does not affect the final outcome, the effect of raining on human body.

2.4.11. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.33 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about the conditio per quam relationship $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio per quam relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c + d) - A)^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A}\end{aligned}\tag{73}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b + d))^2}{B} + \frac{((a + c) - B)^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B}\end{aligned}\tag{74}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of the conditio per quam relationship/distribution $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis is accepted. Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.4.12. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship

Definition 2.34 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of the conditio per quam relationship can be calculated

as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \rightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(b/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

Again, a low p-value indicates a statistical significance.

2.4.13. Necessary and sufficient conditions

Definition 2.35 (Necessary and sufficient conditions [EQV]).

The necessary and sufficient condition (EQV) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + d}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$

2.4.14. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.36 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

Even the necessary and sufficient condition relationship $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \\ &\quad \frac{d - ((c+d))^2}{\underline{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{d - ((b + d))^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + \frac{b^2}{B}\end{aligned}\quad (78)$$

The calculated $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . Under conditions where the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship/distribution $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$, the $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero. It is to be cleared whether Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction should be used at all.

2.4.15. The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.37 (The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((b+c)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (79)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. Table 11 may provide an overview of the theoretical distribution of a necessary and sufficient condition.

Table 11. Necessary and sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	1	0	1
	NO	0	1	1
		1	1	2

2.4.16. Either or conditions

Definition 2.38 (Either A_t or B_t conditions [NEQV]).

Mathematically, an either A_t or B_t condition relationship (NEQV), denoted by $p(A_t \succ\prec B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \succ\prec B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \wedge \underline{B}_t) \vee (\underline{A}_t \wedge B_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + c}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{80}$$

It is $p(A_t \succ\prec B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 12).

Table 12. Either A_t or B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	1	1
	NO	1	0	1
		1	1	2

2.4.17. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.39 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship).

An either or condition relationship $p(A_t \succ\prec B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \succ\prec B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \\
 &\quad \frac{c - ((c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + \frac{d^2}{\underline{A}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{81}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \succ\prec B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{b - ((b + d))^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + \frac{d^2}{B}\end{aligned}\quad (82)$$

Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.4.18. The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.40 (The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of an either or condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \succ\prec B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \succ\prec B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+d)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (83)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance.

2.4.19. Causal relationship k

Definition 2.41 (Causal relationship k).

Nonetheless, mathematically, the causal (Barukčić, 2011a,b, 2012) relationship (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017b) between a cause U_t (German: Ursache) and an effect W_t (German: Wirkung), denoted by $k(U_t, W_t)$, is defined *at each single Bernoulli trial t* in terms of statistics and probability theory as

$$\begin{aligned}k(U_t, W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma(U_t, W_t)}{\sigma(U_t) \times \sigma(W_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{p(U_t \wedge W_t) - p(U_t) \times p(W_t)}{\sqrt{(p(U_t) \times (1 - p(U_t))) \times (p(W_t) \times (1 - p(W_t)))}}\end{aligned}\quad (84)$$

where $\sigma(U_t, W_t)$ denotes the co-variance between a cause U_t and an effect W_t *at every single Bernoulli trial t*, $\sigma(U_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of a cause U_t at the same single Bernoulli trial t, $\sigma(W_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of an effect W_t at same single Bernoulli trial t. Table 13 illustrates the theoretically possible relationships between a cause and an effect.

Table 13. Sample space and the causal relationship k

		Effect B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(U_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

2.5. Statistical methods

The probability of the necessary (Barukčić, 2021d) condition $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated and tested for statistical significance. The probability of the sufficient (Barukčić, 2021d) condition $p(\text{IMP})$ has been calculated, the statistical significance of this relationship has been proofed. The chi-square goodness of fit test with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit a certain theoretical distribution in the population. The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2021d) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events/factors analysed. The hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922, Gonin, 1936, Huygens and van Schooten, 1657, Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided significance of the causal relationship k. The study (design) bias has been controlled by IOI, the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) and IOU, the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019b). All the data were analysed using MS Excel (Microsoft Corporation, USA). The p values less than 0.05 were considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

2.6. Axioms

2.6.1. Axiom I. Lex identitatis

In this context, we define axiom I as the expression

$$+ 1 = +1 \quad (85)$$

2.6.2. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis

In this context, axiom II or **lex contradictionis**, the negative of lex identitatis, or

$$+ 0 = +1 \quad (86)$$

and equally the most simple form of a contradiction formulated.

2.6.3. Axiom III. Lex negationis

$$\neg(0) \times 0 = 1 \quad (87)$$

where \neg denotes (logical (Boole, 1854) or natural) negation (Ayer, 1952, Förster and Melamed, 2012, Hedwig, 1980, Heinemann, 1943, Horn, 1989, Koch, 1999, Kunen, 1987, Newstadt, 2015, Royce, 1917, Speranza and Horn, 2010, Wedin, 1990). In this context, there is some evidence that $\neg(1) \times 1 = 0$. In other words, it is $(\neg(1) \times 1) \times (\neg(0) \times 0) = 1$

3. Results

3.1. Mutually exclusive events and drug or vaccine efficacy

Theorem 3.1 (Mutually exclusive events and drug or vaccine efficacy). *The mutually exclusive event's relationship is the determining part of the vaccine efficacy as*

$$VE(A_t, B_t) \equiv (p(A_t | B_t)) \times 100 \equiv (p(A_t \uparrow B_t)) \times 100 \equiv (1 - p(a_t)) \times 100 \quad (88)$$

Proof by direct proof. The premise

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (89)$$

is true. In the following, we rearrange the premise. The relative risk(see [Cornfield, 1951](#), [Sadovsky et al., 1953](#)) $RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}$ is equal to itself. It is

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \quad (90)$$

or

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)} \quad (91)$$

Rearranging equation 106, it is

$$1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(1 - \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)}\right) \quad (92)$$

or

$$(1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times 100 \equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)}\right)\right) \times 100 \quad (93)$$

The vaccine efficacy (VE) as proposed by Greenwood and Yule([Greenwood and Yule, 1915](#)) in 1915 follows as

$$VE(A_t, B_t) \equiv (1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times 100 \equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)}\right)\right) \times 100 \quad (94)$$

Equation 94 simplifies as

$$VE(A_t, B_t) \equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)}\right)\right) \times 100 \quad (95)$$

or as

$$\frac{VE(A_t, B_t)}{100} \equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)}\right)\right) \quad (96)$$

Rearranging equation 96, it is

$$\frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)} \equiv \left(1 - \left(\frac{VE(A_t, B_t)}{100}\right)\right) \quad (97)$$

or

$$p(a_t) \equiv \left(1 - \left(\frac{VE(A_t, B_t)}{100}\right)\right) \times \frac{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)} \quad (98)$$

The exclusion relationship (see equation 57) follows as

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(a_t) \equiv 1 - \left(1 - \left(\frac{VE(A_t, B_t)}{100}\right)\right) \times \frac{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)} \quad (99)$$

In the following, we consider conditions where $\frac{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)} \equiv 1$. We obtain

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(a_t) \equiv 1 - \left(1 - \left(\frac{VE(A_t, B_t)}{100}\right)\right) \quad (100)$$

or

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(a_t) \equiv \left(\frac{VE(A_t, B_t)}{100}\right) \quad (101)$$

In other words, it is

$$VE(A_t, B_t) \equiv (p(A_t | B_t)) \times 100 \equiv (p(A_t \uparrow B_t)) \times 100 \equiv (1 - p(a_t)) \times 100 \quad (102)$$

□

Remark 3.1. A reader may be inclined to note that conditions like $\frac{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)} \equiv 1$ do not really exist. Such a reasoning is of course logically incorrect and unsound. The philosophy of placebo controlled trials demand conditions where $p(A_t) \equiv p(NotA_t)$. At the end, it has to be that $N \times p(c_t) \equiv +1$ which formally does exist. However, one of the main tasks of theorem 3.1 is to provide striking evidence that the exclusion relationship can be the only logical foundation of drug or vaccine efficacy and not the relative risk.

3.2. Mutually exclusive events and drug or vaccine efficacy

Theorem 3.2 (Mutually exclusive events and drug or vaccine efficacy). *In general, the placebo group independent drug or vaccine efficacy et cetera can be calculated approximately (see Barukčić, 2021a) as*

$$VE(A_t, B_t) \geq \left(\left(1 - \frac{N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(A_t)}\right)\right) \times 100 \equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{E(a_t)}{E(A_t)}\right)\right) \times 100 \quad (103)$$

where $E(a_t)$ is the expectation value of the two events A_t and B_t at a certain Bernoulli trial t , $E(A_t)$ is the expectation value of the event A_t (a condition, a drug, a vaccine, a risk factor et cetera).

Proof by direct proof. The premise

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (104)$$

is true. In the following, we rearrange the premise. The relative risk(see [Cornfield, 1951](#), [Sadowsky et al., 1953](#)) $RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}$ is equal to itself. It is

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \quad (105)$$

or

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)} \quad (106)$$

Rearranging equation 106, it is

$$1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(1 - \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)} \right) \quad (107)$$

or

$$(1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times 100 \equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)} \right) \right) \times 100 \quad (108)$$

The vaccine efficacy (VE) as proposed by Greenwood and Yule([Greenwood and Yule, 1915](#)) in 1915 follows as

$$VE(A_t, B_t) \equiv (1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times 100 \equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)} \right) \right) \times 100 \quad (109)$$

In the following we consider placebo group independent conditions where $p(NotA_t) \equiv p(c_t)$. Equation 109 becomes

$$\begin{aligned} VE(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} \right) \right) \times 100 \\ &\equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(A_t)} \right) \right) \times 100 \\ &\equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{E(a_t)}{E(A_t)} \right) \right) \times 100 \\ &\equiv \left(\left(1 - \frac{a}{A} \right) \right) \times 100 \end{aligned} \quad (110)$$

□

Remark 3.2. *A very critical reader will not hesitate to point out that considering placebo group independent conditions where $p(NotA_t) \equiv p(c_t)$ is of no practical use. However, such an attitude would be unworldly.*

3.3. How effective is the ChAdOx1 nCov-19 Covid-19 vaccine?

Theorem 3.3. *The 1915-year method of calculating the vaccine efficacy as published by Greenwood and Yule (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) is very misleading, if not wrong in important ways.*

Proof. Voysey et al. investigated the effect of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 (AZD1222) vaccine on “12282 participants in the ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 group and ... 11962 participants in the control group ... There were seven deaths considered unrelated to vaccination (two in the ChAdOx1 nCov-19 group and five in the control group)”¹³. The overall vaccine efficacy has been reported as 66,7%. It was possible to calculate the vaccine efficacy of AstraZeneca’s ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine ex post (see table 3). Based on the data of Grange et al. (see Grange et al., 2021), the vaccine efficacy of AstraZeneca’s ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine ex post according to Greenwood and Yule (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) is 99,5269%. However, the placebo group independent approximate(see Barukčić, 2021a) drug i.e. vaccine efficacy (VE approx.) of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine is approximately (see equation 58) greater than or equal to 99,0721539% (see equation 6). The original data of AstraZeneca’s ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine study suggest a vaccine efficacy of 61,04217554 % (see equation 1). However, based on the original data, the placebo group independent approximate(see Barukčić, 2021a) drug i.e. vaccine efficacy (VE approx.) of AstraZeneca’s ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine has been calculated approximately (see equation 58) as greater than or equal to 99,98371601 % (see equation 2). In contrast to the method of Greenwood and Yule (Greenwood and Yule, 1915), the original data of AstraZeneca’s ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine study provide evidence, that the of AstraZeneca’s ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine is effective with more than 99,98371601 %. The original data allow us to conclude that the AstraZeneca’s ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine is highly effective (99,98371601 % and even more) but not if we rely on the 1915-year method of Greenwood and Yule (Greenwood and Yule, 1915). The 1915-year method of Greenwood and Yule (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) is very misleading, if not wrong in important ways. Inappropriate statistical methods can lead to serious errors. □

3.4. How effective is the BNT162b2 Covid-19 vaccine ex post?

Theorem 3.4. *Polack et al.¹⁴ reported that “43,448 received injections: 21,720 with BNT162b2 and 21,728 with placebo. There were 8 cases of Covid-19 ... among participants assigned to receive BNT162b2 and 162 cases among those assigned to placebo; BNT162b2 was 95% effective in preventing Covid-19’’. The exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.*

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{Vaccine : BNT162b2} \mid \text{COVID} - 19(\text{infection})) &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - p(a_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - \left(\frac{8}{43448} \right) \\
 &\equiv +0,99981587
 \end{aligned} \tag{111}$$

¹³PMID: 33617777

¹⁴PMID: 33301246

with a P Value = 0,000184. The published vaccine efficacy (VE) is calculated (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 VE(\text{BNT162b2 vaccine, Covid-19 infection}) &\equiv \left(1 - \left(\frac{a_t \times A_t}{A_t \times c_t}\right)\right) \times 100 \\
 &\equiv \left(1 - \left(\frac{8 \times 21728}{21720 \times 162}\right)\right) \times 100 \quad (112) \\
 &\equiv 95,05990951
 \end{aligned}$$

or 95,05990951 %.

Inside table 14 it is assumed that the event Covid-19 death occurred or would occur 79953 times in the group of 4121574 non-BNT162b2 Covid-19 vaccinated inhabitants of Scotland.

Table 14. BNT162b2 Covid-19 vaccine and Covid-19 death (Study Grange et al. , 2021).

		Covid-19 death		
		YES	NO	
BNT162b2 Covid-19 vaccine	YES	47	1246979	1247026
	NO	79953	4041621	4121574
		80000	5288600	5368600

Statistical analysis.

Causal relationship k = -0,0674809210
 p Value left tailed (HGD) = 0,0000000
p (EXCL) = 0,9999912454
p (EXCL) approx. = 0,9999623103
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_t) = 0,0018
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_t) = 0,0276
 p Value (EXCL) = 0,0000087546

Relative risk (RR).

RR (nc) = 0,0019
 RR (sc) = 0,0025
 Vaccine efficacy (%) = 99,8057

Additional measures.

OR = 1,0000
 IOR = -0,9975

Study design.

p(IOU)= 0,752817122
 p(IOI)= 0,21737995

The placebo group independent approximate(see Barukčić, 2021a) drug i.e. vaccine efficacy (VE

approx.) of the BNT162b2 Covid-19 vaccine follows approximately (see equation 58) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 VE_{approx.}(A_t, B_t) &\geq \left(1 - \frac{N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(A_t)}\right) \times 100 \\
 &\geq \left(1 - \left(\frac{47}{1247026}\right)\right) \times 100 \\
 &\geq 99,99623103\%
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{113}$$

In other words, less than 3-4 out of 1 000 000 participants would die due to a Covid-19 infection even if vaccinated by the BNT162b2 Covid-19 vaccine. Under conditions of a fair study design, it was pre-calculated and predicted that the mRNA BNT162b2 Covid-19 vaccine is of no help for 4 out of 1.000.000 persons (see Barukčić, 2021c). The agreement between prediction and true value is amazing.

4. Discussion

A successful vaccine can be of help to protect single persons against bacterial, fungal, parasitic, or viral infections et cetera. But to be effective in humans, even to fight down a certain disease and to prevent human societies from devastating consequences, even globally, it is appropriate if a vaccine induces humoral and cellular responses. In particular, mRNA vaccines are one safe and efficient alternative to protein-, recombinant virus- or DNA-based vaccines. The presence of appropriate (levels of) immunoglobulins in the serum ¹⁵ of a patient is of use to overcome a severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2) infection quickly. **Whether or not an administration of several SARS-CoV-2 vaccine doses at short intervals under therapeutic aspects (in order to trigger a quick, self-produced IgG production directed against SARS-CoV-2) during an acute SARS-CoV-2 infection makes any sense, remains to be studied by further investigations.** In this context, decisions are and need to be made not on the basis of ideological dogma but on the grounds of facts and objective criteria. However, decisions do not necessarily have to concur with objective reality and cannot be defended or justified for any cause. In addition to these considerations, and taking into account the need for ideology-free political, scientific and other decisions, a good study design, the obligation to be very precise when collecting the data et cetera and the selection of logically consistent statistical methods for evaluating the collected data is of no less importance. As it has been demonstrated strongly beyond all possible, reasonable and every shadow of a doubt, the concept of vaccine efficacy as advocated by Greenwood and Yule (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) is full of contradictions and for this reason of minor importance.

¹⁵PMID: 33552760

5. Conclusion

We cannot rely on Greenwood and Yule's statistical concept of vaccine efficacy to the appropriate extent necessary; therefore, this concept should be abandoned completely.

Acknowledgments

No funding or any financial support by a third party was received.

Patient consent for publication

Not required.

Conflict of interest statement

No conflict of interest to declare.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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